

WELLNESS TOURISM MODEL BY THE NEW NORMAL THE SOUTHERN ANDAMAN REGION

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Abstract

Wellness tourism in Thailand was facing the problem of natural calamities, a lack of life and their belonging security, and service staffs with limited proficiency in foreign language communication, that all contribute to the negative image of services. The objectives of this research were to: 1) study the importance of factors influencing the wellness tourism promotion by the new normal in the southern Andaman region; 2) study tourist behavior. Infrastructure, public relations, and tourism standard which influencing the wellness tourism promotion by the new normal; and 3) proposed a new model of wellness tourism promotion by the new normal in the southern Andaman region. This research used mixed research which is quantitative research and qualitative research. The quantitative research sample consisted of 360 business entrepreneurs in the southern Andaman region, obtained from stratified sampling and using the criteria 20 times of 18 observation variables. The tool was a questionnaire. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and analyzed using a structural equation model. Qualitative Research used a semi-structured interview with a sample of 17 people, including executives, government officials. Wellness tourism business entrepreneurs, Tourism Association of Thailand, tour leader and tourists. The results of the research found that: 1) tourist behavior, infrastructure, public relations, tourism standard, and the promotion of wellness tourism is of high importance; 2) Factors influencing the promotion of wellness tourism in a new normal were tourist behavior, tourism standard, public relations, and infrastructure, respectively; and 3) Wellness tourism model by the new normal in the southern Andaman region follows the following principles: cultivating quality personnel capable of adapting to the new normal's context for tourism, diversifying tourism and adding value to Wellness products and services, modifying the environment to make it more facilitating to wellness tourists; and choosing locally sourced, high-quality, organics ingredients. The research findings can help to private business owners in tourism business in determining the management direction for promoting wellness tourism that complies with standards for the safety of people and property.

Keywords: Promoting Wellness Tourism / New Normal / Southern Andaman Region

Introduction

Thailand's tourism industry is growing rapidly. Both the public and private sectors have clear policies to encourage and encourage each area or province to develop the community's resources into tourist attractions to attract more tourists. The trend in Wellness tourism has been popular with Wellness -conscious tourists and responds to the trend of Wellness promotion activities such as spas, beauty treatments, Thai massages, or even mineral baths soaking in healthy hot springs in the provinces of Thailand (Tourism Authority of Thailand (TAT), 2017).

Thailand has been developed and promoted as a hub. Wellness Tourism for Thailand's Development Strategy as an International Health Center in April 2018, Samitivej Hospital was

selected as one of the top 5 healthcare facilities in the world by announcing the results of the 2018 ranking of the 10 Best Hospitals for Wellness Tourism at the International Tourism Expo (ITB) 2018 in Berlin, Germany. Wellness tourism is a journey that involves the pursuit of maintenance or strengthening of a person's Wellness, covering all services that provide holistic preventive care and improvement of Wellness (Global Wellness Institute, 2017).

Wellness tourism is divided into 2 types of services within and outside the industry. It can be divided into 2 categories according to the nature of the service, namely internal and external health care services, such as internal health care services such as healthy nutrition counseling services, physical and mental integrity, personalized preventive medicine as well as supplements and alternative medicines, etc. External healthcare services are common examples such as beauty and anti-aging businesses, spas, massages, and wellness tourism, where health-related activities tend to cost more than regular activities. As a result, health travellers agree to pay for an invaluable experience. Foreign health travellers coming to Thailand also face insecurity in relation to natural disasters, life and property. The ability to communicate in a foreign language of the personnel providing the services, the poor image of the service such as covert or non-standard spa services, and the length of stay of foreigners and their dependents are not conducive to the treatment of certain diseases that require a long time. Also due to COVID-19. More than 25 million people have already been infected worldwide, resulting in tourism. Whether domestic or international, disruption. While there is still uncertainty about vaccines, and even if there is a vaccine, it doesn't solve every problem immediately, as vaccinated people can still contract the disease and become carriers. Therefore, the tourism business needs to rely mainly on domestic tourists; tourism in the new normal era is "Thai tourism, close proximity and safe travel", although it is possible to travel abroad. Given the higher risk of infection in Thailand, a shorter trip to Thailand, as driving is a safer way to get out of infection than it is. Visit unseen is not crowded, as the most popular tourist destinations in the country may have already been, and unseen places with few people make it safer from infection. Thai tourist revenue will become the main revenue, accounting for more than 60% in 2020-2021 from 36% in 2019 (Department of Disease Control, Ministry of Health, 2021).

From such a problem condition. The researchers are interested in studying the "Wellness tourism model by the new normal the southern Andaman region" because the Southern Andaman provinces have a diverse and high potential tourism resource base, especially the outstanding marine and land tourism resources, and the global reputation is able to develop and enhance the quality of basic services and facilities to be adequate and meet safety standards in order to promote, support and empower entrepreneurs to develop Wellness tourism according to the new model to be concrete and practical.

Research objectives

1. To study the importance of factors influencing the promotion of new Wellness tourism in the Southern Andaman Region.
2. To study tourist behavior, infrastructure, public relations, tourism standards that has an impact on promoting Wellness tourism according to the new normal.

3. To propose a new model of promoting wellness tourism in the Southern Andaman Region.

Research hypothesis

1. Tourist behavior, infrastructure, public relations, Tourism standards is based on promoting Wellness tourism in a new way.
2. Tourist behavior, infrastructure, public relations depend on tourism standards.
3. Tourist behavior, infrastructure depends on public relations.
4. Tourist behavior depends on infrastructure

Research Methodology

This research uses mixed methods of quantitative research and qualitative research to collect information related to behavior, infrastructure, public relations, and tourism standards. And promoting wellness tourism based on new trajectories and confirming quantitative findings.

Quantitative research is a study of documents and data generated to generate questionnaires to collect data with a sample of healthcare entrepreneurs in the southern Andaman Sea. Check the quality of the tool by finding content-based match values between .60-1.00, the confidence of the entire questionnaire is .957.

Qualitative Research We analyzed the influence of the four latent variables affecting the promotion of wellness tourism, according to the new model and created semi-structured interviews and in-depth interviews with five groups of 17 key informants. Analyze content to confirm quantitative findings and present a new model for promoting wellness tourism in the Southern Andaman Region.

Findings

The level of the five factors studied, the sample commented on, was the highest level of all 5 factors. The promotion of wellness tourism, according to the new model is the 1st most valuable, followed by tourist behavior, infrastructure, public relations, tourism standards, respectively, according to Table 1.

Table 1: Mean levels, standard deviations, and sequence of factors studied

Factors Studied	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	Interpret the results	Order
Tourist Behavior	3.85	0.48	High	2
Infrastructure	3.83	0.47	High	3
Public Relations	3.77	0.57	High	4
Tourism Standards	3.77	0.47	High	5
Promoting Wellness Tourism in the New Normal	3.90	0.44	High	1

The results of the analysis of structural equations can present an alternative relationship structure model (Estimates) according to Figure 1.

Figure 1: An alternative relationship structure model (Estimates)

In Figure 1, the results of the analysis of alternative models showed that external latent variables, tourist behavior (TOBE), directly affect infrastructure (INFR), public relations (PURE), tourism standards (TOST), and wellness tourism promotion (PNNH), equal to 0.80, 0.45, 0.46, and 0.35, respectively. Infrastructure (INFR) directly affecting public relations (PURE), tourism standards (TOST) and wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) were 0.51, 0.26 and 0.15 respectively. Public relations section (PURE) directly affecting tourism standards (TOST) and wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) were 0.28 and 0.22, respectively. And tourism standards (TOST) directly affect the promotion of wellness tourism (PNNH) of 0.34, can present the influence values of the latent variables studied in Table 2.

Table 2: Analyzes aggregate relationships, direct relationships, and indirect relationships of alternative models

Dependent variables	Relation ship	Independent variables				
		TOBE	INFR	PURE	TOST	PNNH
INFR	DE	0.80**	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	IE	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	TE	0.80**	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
PURE	DE	0.45**	0.51**	N/A	N/A	N/A
	IE	0.41**	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	TE	0.86**	0.51**	N/A	N/A	N/A
TOST	DE	0.46**	0.26**	0.28**	N/A	N/A
	IE	0.45**	0.14**	N/A	N/A	N/A
	TE	0.91**	0.40**	0.28**	N/A	N/A
PNNH	DE	0.35**	0.15*	0.22*	0.34**	N/A
	IE	0.54**	0.25**	0.10*	N/A	N/A
	TE	0.89**	0.40**	0.32**	0.34**	N/A

Chi-Square= 72.91, df=73, p-value = 0.481, GFI=0.98, AGFI=0.95, RMR=0.006, RMSEA=0.000, CFI=1.00, CN= 503.62

From Table 2, it can be described that tourist behavior (TOBE) has the highest direct impact on infrastructure (INFR) as much as 0.80, followed by tourism standards (TOST), public relations (PURE) and wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) of 0.45, 0.46 and 0.35 respectively, and indirectly affects the promotion of wellness tourism (PNNH), tourism standards (TOST) and public relations (PURE) of 0.54, 0.45 and 0.41, respectively.

Infrastructure (INFR) has the highest direct impact on public relations (PURE) of 0.51, followed by tourism standards (TOST) and Wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) of 0.26 and 0.15, respectively, and indirectly affects wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) and tourism standards (TOST) of 0.25 and 0.14, respectively.

Public relations (PURE) have the highest direct impact on tourism standards (TOST) of 0.28, followed by the direct effect on the promotion of Wellness tourism (PNNH) of 0.22, and indirectly to the promotion of wellness tourism (PNNH) of 0.10. And found that the tourism standards (TOST). The direct result of promoting wellness tourism (PNNH) was 0.34.

From the correlation between internal variables and external latent variables. There is a very high level of positive correlation (with a statistical value r would be 0.80-0.91). There are couples with very high and very high levels of correlation, including public relations (PURE) with tourism standards (TOST) and tourist behavior (TOBE) with tourism standards (TOST) equal to 0.91. This is followed by tourism standards (TOST) and Wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) equal to 0.90 tourist behavior (TOBE) with Wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) is equal to 0.89 infrastructure (INFR) with tourism standards (TOST) is equal to 0.88 public relations (PURE) with infrastructure (INFR) and public relations (PURE) with Wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) is equal to 0.87. Public relations (PURE) with tourist behavior (TOBE) are equal to 0.86 infrastructures (INFR) with wellness tourism promotion (PNNH) is equal to 0.82, and infrastructure (INFR) with tourist behavior (TOBE) is equal to 0.80.

It also found that the structural equations of infrastructure, public relations, tourism standards, and Wellness tourism promotion were also found. R2 is equal to 0.64, 0.74, 0.83, and 0.79, respectively. It shows that hypothetical relationship structure models can explain the variability of infrastructure, public relations, tourism standards, and wellness tourism promotion by 64 percent, 74, 83, and 79 percent, respectively.

The results of the overall visual analysis showed that the harmonization index values were more consistent with empirical data, meeting benchmarks that represented model consistency and empirical data with very good standards.

Table 3: Hypothetical test results

Research Hypothesis	Path coefficient	t statistics	Result
Hypothesis 1: Tourist behavior, infrastructure, public relations and tourism standards affect the promotion of Wellness tourism.			
1.1 Tourist behavior directly affects the promotion of wellness tourism (TOBE --> PNNH)	0.35**	3.77	Support
1.2 Infrastructure directly affects the promotion of Wellness tourism (INFR --> PNNH)	0.15*	1.98	Support
1.3 Public relations directly affect the promotion of wellness tourism (PURE --> PNNH)	0.22*	2.03	Support
1.4 Tourism standards directly affect the promotion of wellness tourism (TOST --> PNNH)	0.34**	2.58	Support
Assumption 2: Tourist behavior infrastructure and public relations affect tourism standards			
2.1 tourist behavior directly affects tourism standards (TOBE --> TOST)	0.46**	7.42	Support
2.2 infrastructures directly affect tourism standards (INFR --> TOST)	0.26**	3.26	Support
2.3 public relations directly affect tourism standards (PURE --> TOST)	0.28**	2.81	Support
Assumption 3: Behavior and infrastructure affect public relations.			
3.1 Tourist behavior directly affects public relations (TOBE --> PURE)	0.45**	6.63	Support
3.2 Infrastructure directly affects relations. (INFR --> PURE)	0.51**	6.79	Support
Assumption 4: tourist behavior affects infrastructure			
4.1 tourist behavior directly affects public relations (TOBE --> INFR)	0.80**	15.07	Support

Note ** mean p value ≤ 0.01 ; * mean p value ≤ 0.05

From Table 3, the results of the hypothesis test can be summarized as follows:

Hypothesis 1: Tourist behavior, infrastructure, public relations, and tourism standards affect the promotion of wellness tourism. The t statistics are 3.77, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis at the level of 0.01, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables in the same direction. This has resulted in the promotion of wellness tourism.

Infrastructure directly affects the promotion of wellness tourism, with a path coefficient of 0.15, t statistics equal to 1.98, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis of 0.05, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables studied in the same direction.

Public relations directly affect the promotion of wellness tourism, with a path coefficient of 0.22, t statistics equal to 2.03, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis of 0.05, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables studied in the same direction.

Tourism standards have a direct impact on the promotion of wellness tourism, with a path coefficient of 0.34, t statistics of 2.58, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis of 0.01, which can be interpreted as the variables studied correlating in the same direction.

Hypothesis 2: Tourist behavior infrastructure and public relations affect tourism standards. The t statistics are 7.42, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis of 0.01, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables in the same direction. More and more resulted in greater standards.

Infrastructure directly affects the path coefficient of 0.26, the t statistics value is 3.26, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis at the level of 0.01, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables in the same direction, more and more resulted in greater standards.

Public relations directly affect tourism standards, with a path coefficient of 0.28, t statistics equal to 2.81, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis at the level of 0.01, which can be interpreted as correlating in the same direction. More and more resulted in greater standards.

Hypothesis 3: Tourist behavior and infrastructure affect public relations Based on the results of the hypothesis test; tourist behavior has a direct effect on public relations. The t statistics are 6.63, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis of 0.01, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables in the same direction, more and more resulting in greater public relations as well.

Infrastructure directly affects public relations, with a path coefficient of 0.51, t statistics equal to 6.79, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis at the level of 0.01, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables in the same direction, more and more resulting in greater public relations as well.

Hypothesis 4: tourist behavior affects infrastructure Based on the results of the hypothesis test; tourist behavior has a direct effect on infrastructure. The t statistics are 15.07, which supports the statistically significant hypothesis at the level of 0.01, which can be interpreted as correlating the variables studied in the same direction, that is, when the behavior is correlated, more and more resulted in more infrastructure as well.

The wellness tourism model of the new normal the southern Andaman region follows: Developing quality personnel to be able to adapt to the context of new tourism, adjusting the place to facilitate healthy tourists, choosing locally sourced raw materials as good quality and non-toxic, focusing on diversifying tourism and adding value to health products and services.

Discussion

The behavior of tourists has a positive influence on the promotion of new Wellness tourism in the Southern Andaman Region, as tourists engage in activities through a decision-making process to travel and respond to their needs. Corresponds to Pashriya Kaewshu (2021) believes that the decision-making process for tourism determines the actions of tourists. And In line with Bandage (2020) studied the attitudes of tourists using public transport services: policy implications from a Maltese case study. It was found that the nature and quality of service of public buses need to be improved because it negatively affects other factors that influence the attitude of tourists.

Infrastructure has a positive influence on the promotion of new wellness tourism in the Southern Andaman Region, as infrastructure is what supports the tourism industry, enabling tourism to operate well. Electrical system, plumbing system, public transport, public health system, communication system, technology system these are important elements that make travel easy and fast to connect with each other. Correspondence with Amir, F. A., Ismawi Ismail, M. N., & See, T. P. (2015) Identifies tourism-related infrastructure as a supply chain that works together to create attractiveness to local tourist attractions.

Consistent with Carmigniani, J, Furht B, editors. (2011) Studies have found that the infrastructure of tourist attractions, namely price, information acquisition, quality of service, and variety of accommodation facilities are important in deciding which attractions are important in deciding on tourist attractions. Liu, H. And Chang, F. (2013) Stated that when a crisis situation leads to insecurity resulting in a decrease in tourists, preventing tourists from cancelling a hotel is necessary to manage hotel information, provide security equipment, or provide security personnel for tourists.

Public relations have a positive influence on the promotion of new wellness tourism in the Southern Andaman Region due to various business organizations. It is necessary to communicate with public relations by operating in various forms related to the production and public relations. In line with Chiranjib Kumar. (2021), it was found that tourists were positively correlated with the use of social media to access information during a crisis while travelling. Erciş, A., Ünal, S., Candan, F. B., Yıldırım, H. (2012).

Implementing planned activities to build public understanding, acceptance and evaluation. In line with the Global Wellness Institute (2014), public relations are a series of five activities: research, clear objective determination, strategy formulation, planned performance, and performance evaluation.

Tourism standards have a positive influence on the promotion of new wellness tourism in the Southern Andaman Region as the standards give tourists a sense of confidence in their service and ultimately a pleasant impression. In line with Kipper, G., Rampolla, J. (2013) A study of tourist safety and security in San Augustine County found that the sample perceived to be involved in safety, protecting the tourist environment, and tourist attractions.

The key players in ensuring the safety of tourists are the local government, the main way to improve tourist safety is education and training for personnel, and the most important factor that causes or failures related to tourism safety is overcrowding of tourist attractions. According to Lana Kordić -Blank and Blanka Šimundić (2021), the majority of tourists are American and European, the perception of the safety of attractions depends on the tour guide, friendly environment and tourist attractions are well prepared about safety, especially the presence of CCTV cameras at tourist attractions, and the presence of tourist police in and out of uniform helps ensure safety. Therefore, having a safety facility is important when choosing a tourist attraction.

Suggestion

Academic feedback

This finding confirms the findings that are consistent with the concepts, theories, and related research contributions that the researchers reviewed, with the knowledge gained being used to establish a new approach to the optimization of Wellness tourism promotion. Wellness tourism entrepreneurs can use it as a way to transform tourism development to better meet the needs of customers.

Suggestions for future research

1. Study the satisfaction of the new Wellness tourism promotion model in the Southern Andaman Region.
2. Study the development of Wellness tourism promotion in the Northern Region.

Reference

- Amir, F. A., Ismawi Ismail, M. N., & See, T. P. (2015). Sustainable Tourist Environment: Bandage. (2020). Virtual Tourism. Retrieved <https://www.brandage.com/article/18405/Google>. Retrieved 2 July 2020.
- Carmigniani, J, Furht B, editors. (2011). Handbook of Augmented Reality. New York: Springer.
- Chen, K.; Liu, H. And Chang, F. (2013). Essential Customer Service Factors and the Segmentation of Older Visitors within Wellness Tourism Based on Hot Springs Hotels. International Journal of Hospitality Management. 35:122-132.
- Chiranjib Kumar. (2021). Ecotourism and Wellness tourism a solution to Corona. Corona Pandemic: Opportunities and Solutions, Gambella University Ethiopia.
- Department of Disease Control, Ministry of Health. (2021). Guidelines for the implementation of COVID-19 cases for establishments. Nonhaburi: Graphic & Design Publishing House.
- Erciş, A., Ünal, S., Candan, F. B., & Yıldırım, H. (2012). The effect of brand satisfaction, trust and brand commitment on loyalty and repurchase intentions. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences, 58, 1395-1404.
- Global Wellness Institute. (2014). Global Spa & Wellness Economy Monitor. New York: Global Wellness Institute.
- Kipper, G. & Rampolla, J. (2013). Augmented Reality: A merging Technologies Guide to AR. Massachusetts: Elsevier.

Lana Kordić -Blank and Blanka Šimundić. (2021). The Efficiency of Wellness Tourism Infrastructure in Croatia. Conference: International Days of Statistics and Economics At: Prague, Czech Republic, February 2021.

Lumpur. Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences, 168 (2015), 123 – 133.

Pashriya Kaewshu. (2021). Factors influencing the change in tourism habits in the new normal after the COVID-19 pandemic. Bangkok: Faculty of Business Administration, Ramkhamhaeng University.

Perception of international women travelers of safety and security in Kuala

Tourism Authority of Thailand (TAT). (2017). Thailand's Wellness tourism awareness level survey project. Bangkok: Planning Policy Department, Tourism Planning Division.